

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION 1 – TABLES

TITLE: GAMMA/DELTA T CELL NEOPLASMS: HOW MANY AND HOW DIFFERENT?

Author: Margarida Lima

Table S1. Clinical and laboratory features of patients with gamma/delta T cell large granular lymphocyte leukemia, as compared to patients with T cell large granular lymphocyte leukemia in general

Author, year	Patients with GDTLGLL					Patients with TLGLL				
	Sandberg, 2006	Bourgault-Rouxel, 2008	Yabe, 2015	Pandolfi, 1990*	Loughran, 1993†	Dhodapkar, 1994	Semenzato, 1997‡ §	Neben, 2003	Bareau, 2010	Yabe, 2015
Reference	[26]	[27]	[28]	[97]	[98]	[99]	[100]	[101]	[49]	[28]
Total number of patients with TLGLL	44	20	14	151	129	68	162	44	201	20
Percentage of GDLGLL cases	100%	100%	100%	NA	<5%	NA	NA	NA	17%	0%
Demographic data										
Age (years) (median; range) (mean ± SD)	63; 34-88	56; 29-82	62; 20-86	55; 5-88	57; 15-88	61; 23-85	60 ± 11	63; 15-87	59; 12-87	61; 42-80
Males / Females (ratio)	24 / 20 (1.4)	9 / 11 (0.82)	11 / 3 (3.7)	86 / 65 (1.3)	57 / 71 (0.80)	34 / 34 (1.0)	71 / 91 (0.78)	22 / 22 (1.0)	90 / 111 (0.81)	13 / 7 (1.9)
Clinical manifestations										
Asymptomatic (% cases)	39%	NA	NA	43%	NA	28%	NA	27%	18%	NA
Systemic symptoms (% cases)	11%	NA	29%	27%	NA	12%	26%	NA	7%	11%
Splenomegaly (% cases)	18%	35%	0%	50%	50%	19%	50%	35%	24%	16%
Hepatomegaly (% cases)	7%	10%	0%	34%	23%	1%	32%	NA	10%	10%
Adenopathy (% cases)	0%	NA	7%	13%	1%	3%	13%	5%	6%	0%
Skin lesions (% cases)	0%	NA	0%	3%	0%	1%	3%	NA	NA	NA
Infections (% cases)	11%	15%	NA	38%	39%	15%	61%	NA	23%	NA
Associated conditions										
Non-hematological neoplasms	2%	NA	14%	7% ‡‡	NA	7%	NA	NA	4%	5%
Mature B cell neoplasms	9%	NA	7% ††	7% ‡‡	NA	0%	NA	NA	5%	10%
Autoimmune diseases	34%	NA	43%	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	33%	25%
Rheumatoid arthritis	16%	20%	43%	18%	28%	26%	36%	20%	19%	10%
Pure red cell aplasia	7%	5%	0%	3%	NA	7%	NA	5%	3%	NA
Autoimmune hemolytic anemia	5%	NA	0%	1%	NA	9%	4%	NA	3%	NA

Author, year	Patients with GDTLGLL					Patients with TLGLL				
	Sandberg, 2006	Bourgault-Rouxel, 2008	Yabe, 2015	Pandolfi, 1990*	Loughran, 1993†	Dhodapkar, 1994	Semenzato, 1997‡ §	Neben, 2003	Bareau, 2010	Yabe, 2015
Reference	[26]	[27]	[28]	[97]	[98]	[99]	[100]	[101]	[49]	[28]
Clinical course and treatment										
Follow-up (months) (median; range)	18 cases ≥ 3 years	34 6-108	43 1-209	29 NA	25 cases ≥ 2 years	44 7-161	23 1-34	47 3-300	58 NA	48 1-101
Clinical course	Indolent	Indolent	Indolent	Indolent	Indolent	Indolent	Indolent	Indolent	Indolent	Indolent
Need for treatment	41%	55%	79%	30%	73%	69%	33%	80%	44%	45%
Deaths	0%	10%	36%	17%	36%	10%	17%	25%	NA	25%
LGLL related deaths	0%	10%	NA	14%	NA	7%	14%	NA	7%	NA
Overall survival	OS 3y 100%	OS 3y 85%	Median OS 62mo	OS 3 y >80%	NA	OS 3y >90% OS 5 y >80%	OS 3 y >80%	NA	OS 3y >90% OS 5y 89%	NS
Laboratorial features										
Leukocytes x 10 ⁹ /l (median, range)	NA	NA	3.8 (1.3-9.7)	NA	NA	4.5 (0.4-37.0)	NA	5.4 (1.0-18.4)	NA	7.2 (2.1-30.6)
Leukocytosis (% cases) (WBC x 10 ⁹ /l)	NA	NA	>5 (43%) >20 (0%)	>5 (83%) >20 (11%)	NA	NA	>5 (78%)	NA	NA	>5 (75%)
Lymphocytes x 10 ⁹ /l (median, range)	NA	NA	2.1 (0.9-7.3)	NA	7.8 (1.0-49.0)	NA	NA	2.8 (0.5-13.0)	NA	3.9 (0.4-24.0)
Lymphocytosis (% cases) (Lymphocytes x 10 ⁹ /l)	NA	>4 (60%)	>4 (29%)	NA	>4 (74%)	>5 (29%)	NA	NA	>4 (51%)	>4 (50%)
Increased LGL (% cases) (LGL x 10 ⁹ /l)	NA	>1 (80%) >4 (45%)	NA	>3 (69%)	>1 (92%) >4 (52%) >10 (14%)	>5 (81%)	>1 (93%)	NA	>1 (64%) >4 (14%)	NA
Neutrophils x 10 ⁹ /l (median, range)	NA	NA	0.6 (0.1-3.4)	NA	NA	0.8	NA	1.3 (0.1-5.7)	NA	1.5 (0.1-3.8)
Neutropenia (% cases) (Neutrophils x 10 ⁹ /l)	<1.5 (48%)	<1.5 (70%) <0.5 (30%)	<1.5 (71%) <0.5 (43%)	<1.5 (64%) <0.5 (37%)	<2.0 (84%) <0.5 (48%)	<1.5 (74%) <0.5 (40%)	<0.5 (37%)	<1.5 (52%) <0.5 (41%)	<1.5 (61%) <0.5 (26%)	<1.5 (50%) <0.5 (15%)
Hemoglobin g/dl (median, range)	NA	NA	11.6 (2.6-15.0)	NA	NA	11.2 (3.6-15.1)	NA	10.4 (6.1-14.7)	NA	11.3 (7.4-17.2)
Anemia (% cases)	<10 (23%)	<10 (10%)	<10 (21%)	<11 (25%)	<10 (49%)	<11.5 (51%)	<10 (26%)	<10 (89%)	<10 (24%)	<10 (35%)

Author, year	Patients with GDTLGLL					Patients with TLGLL				
	Sandberg, 2006	Bourgault-Rouxel, 2008	Yabe, 2015	Pandolfi, 1990*	Loughran, 1993†	Dhodapkar, 1994	Semenzato, 1997‡ §	Neben, 2003	Bareau, 2010	Yabe, 2015
Reference	[26]	[27]	[28]	[97]	[98]	[99]	[100]	[101]	[49]	[28]
(Hemoglobin, g/dl)			<8 (7%)	<9 (11%)		<8 (19%)		<8 (36%)	<8 (7%)	
Platelets x 10 ⁹ /l (median; range)	NA	NA	145 10-295	NA	NA	NA	NA	217 30-634	NA	247 105-647
Thrombocytopenia (% cases) (Platelets x 10 ⁹ /l)	<150 (9%)	<150 (20%)	<150 (50%) <100 (29%) <20 (21%)	<100 (9%)	<150 (19%)	<150 (20%) <20 (1%)	<100 (9%)	<150 (36%) <20 (5%)	<150 (19%)	<150 (15%)
Bone marrow infiltration (% cases)	81%	NA	100%	67%	88%	25% ¶	76%	83%	73%	100%
Abnormal cytogenetics (% cases)	NA	NA**	21%	13%	NA	9%	12%	NA	NA	NA
Immunological abnormalities (% cases)										
Rheumatoid factor	NA	20%	43%	47%	57%	61%	43%	48%	41%	10%
Antinuclear antibodies	NA	NA	NA	39%	38%	44%	38%	48%	48%	NA
Immune complexes	NA	NA	NA	53%	56%	NA	52%	NA	NA	NA
Polyclonal hypergammaglobulinemia	NA	17%	NA	43%	45%	5%	43%	NA	35%	NA
Monoclonal gammopathy	5%	NA	NA	NA	NA	8%	NA	NA	10%	NA
Anti-neutrophil antibodies	NA	NA	NA	NA	41%	20%	NA	NA	NA	NA

Abbreviations: CLPDNK, chronic lymphoproliferative disorders of NK cells; GDLGLL, gamma/delta T-cell large granular lymphocyte leukemia; LGL, large granular lymphocytes; NA, not available; OS, overall survival; TLGLL, T-cell large granular lymphocyte leukemia. Not all cases were tested for all the parameters (please consult the original manuscripts for details).

* This series includes at least 37 patients with CLPDNK.

† This series, comprising 129 patients, include 33 patients from the authors and 99 patients identified based on a Medline computerized search of the published literature

‡ This series includes data of patients from the Pandolfi's series (n=151) and also 11 patients with low LGL count (< 2.0 x 10⁹/l) (Pandolfi, 1990).⁹⁴

§ This series includes at least 38 patients with CLPDNK (37 from the Pandolfi's series).

¶ Evidence of a lymphoproliferative process in the BM was noted in only 16 (25%) patients, although some increase in lymphoid elements was noted in 37 (59%) patients.

** Chromosome 6 deletion was reported in two cases.

†† Another patient was subsequently diagnosed with a large B cell lymphoma.

‡‡ 7% of the patients had associated neoplasms (hematological + non-hematological)

Table S2. TCR-V γ /V δ usage in gamma/delta T-cell large granular lymphocyte leukemia, as compared to peripheral blood gamma/delta T cells from healthy adults.

Author, year	Normal peripheral blood $\gamma\delta$ Tc*		Peripheral blood $\gamma\delta$ Tc from patients with GDTGLL†				Total
	Sandberg, 2006	Lima, 2019	Kuipers, 1994 ‡	Makishima, 2003 §	Sandberg, 2006¶	Bourgault-Rouxel, 2008 **	
References	[26]	Unpublished	[53]	[54]	[26]	[27]	
Number of cases	15	30	3	4	44	20	71
V δ 1	NA (10-20%)	25% (4-67%)	33% (2/3)	100% (3/3)	43% (19/44)	20% (4/20)	40% (28/70)
V δ 2	NA (80-85%)	66% (16-96%)	NT	0% (0/3)	52% (23/44)	70% (14/20)	55% (37/67)
V γ 9	NA (85-90%)	69% (26-97%)	0% (0/3)	100% (3/3)	59% (26/44)	NT	58% (29/50)
V δ 2 + V γ 9	NA	NA	0% (0/3)	0% (0/3)	48% (21/44)	NT	42% (21/50)

Abbreviations: N, number of cases; GDLGLL, gamma/delta T-cell large granular lymphocyte leukemia; PCR, polymerase chain reaction; Tc, T cells. Only series of GDLGLL were considered; most cases published individually in which the TCR-V γ and the TCR-V δ families were tested were found to be V δ 1+ (probable bias).

* Results are presented as median (minimum-maximum) percentages of V δ 1, V δ 2 and V γ 9 Tc among total $\gamma\delta$ Tc.

† Results are presented as frequencies of cases expressing the correspondent V δ and V γ regions.

‡ Immunophenotypic data obtained by FCM studies using anti-TCR-V δ 1 and anti-TCR-V γ 9 monoclonal antibodies.

§ Molecular data obtained by PCR.

¶ Combined molecular data obtained by PCR and immunophenotypic data obtained by FCM demonstrated the V γ 9/V δ 2 phenotype to be present in 21 out of 44 cases (48%), whereas 15 cases (34%) were positive for V δ 1 in combination with V γ other than V γ 9. In four patients (9%), a V γ 9/V δ 2 genotype was detected. The four remaining cases demonstrated expression of V γ 9/V δ 3, V γ 2/V δ 3, V γ 5/V δ 2, and V γ 3/V δ 2. In overall, there was a predominant expression of V γ 9 (n=26; 59%), V δ 2 (n=23; 52%) and V δ 1 (n=19; 43%) in GDTGLL.

** Molecular data revealed that V δ 2 and V δ 1 locus were rearranged in 70% and 20% of cases, respectively

Table S3. TCR-V δ usage in gamma/delta T-cell lymphomas, accordingly to the organs primarily affected.

Organs primarily affected (Lymphoma subtype)	Author, year	Reference numbers	Number of cases	TCR-V δ 1	TCR-V δ 2	TCR-V δ 3
Spleen and liver (HSGDTCL)	Gaulard, 1990	[157]	5	3/5 (60%)	0/5 (0%)	ND
	Ohno, 1993	[158]	1	1/1 (100%)	0/1 (0%)	0/1 (0%)
	Garcia-Sanchez, 1995	[159]	1	1/1 (100%)	0/1 (0%)	0/1 (0%)
	Weidmann, 2000*	[135]	35	20/25 (80%)	0/10 (0%)	ND
	Przybylski, 2000	[160]	11	10/11 (91%)	0/11 (0%)	0/11 (0%)
	Total		53	35/43 (81%)	0/28 (0%)	0/13 (0%)
Skin (PCGDTCL)	Salhany, 1998	[176]	2	0/2 (0%)	2/2 (100%)	0/2 (0%)
	Arnulf, 1998	[174]	2	0/2 (0%)	2/2 (100%)	0/2 (0%)
	Przybylski, 2000	[160]	4	0/4 (0%)	4/4 (100%)	0/4 (0%)
	Saito, 2002	[177]	1	1/1 (100%)	0/1 (0%)	0/1 (0%)
	Total		9	1/9 (11%)	8/9 (89%)	0/9 (0%)
Gastrointestinal tract (including IGDTCCL, EATCL type 2 / MEITCL type)	Arnulf, 1998 (Small bowel)	[174]	2	0/2 (0%)	1/2 (50%)	1/2 (50%)
	Wilson, 2013 (Small bowel)	[48]	5	4/4 (100%)	0/4 (0%)	0/4 (0%)
	Arnulf, 1998 (Stomach)	[174]	1	1/1 (100%)	0/1 (0%)	0/1 (0%)
	Total		7	4/7 (57%)	1/7 (14%)	2/7 (29%)
Respiratory tract	Arnulf, 1998 (Upper, nose)	[174]	3	0/3 (0%)	3/3 (100%)	0/3 (0%)
	Arnulf, 1998 (Upper, larynx)	[174]	1	0/1 (0%)	1/1 (100%)	0/1 (0%)
	Arnulf, 1998 (Lower, lung)	[174]	1	1/1 (100%)	0/1 (0%)	0/1 (0%)
	Total		5	1/5 (20%)	4/5 (80%)	0/5 (0%)

Abbreviations: HSGDTCL, hepatosplenic gamma/delta T cell lymphoma; PCGDTCL, primary cutaneous gamma/delta T cell lymphoma; IGDTCCL, intestinal gamma/delta T cell lymphoma; EATL, enteropathy associated T cell lymphoma; MEITCL, monomorphic epitheliotropic intestinal T-cell lymphoma.

* Includes 45 cases published from 1990 till 2000, from which 35 cases were $\gamma\delta^+$.

Table S4. Immunophenotypic features of gamma/delta T cells in patients with gamma/delta T cell large granular lymphocyte leukemia accordingly to the previously published series.

Author, year	Sun, 1991	Scott, 1994	Kuipers, 1994	Makishima, 2003	Ahmad, 2005	Sandberg, 2006	Shaw, 2008	Chen, 2011	Yabe, 2015	Total
References	[55]	[52]	[53]	[54]	[56]	[26]	[57]	[51]	[28]	All
Number of cases	2	4	3	4	3	44	2	7	14	83
CD2	NT	NT	NT	4/4 (100%)	3/3 (100%)	44/44 (100%)	1/1 (100%)	7/7 (100%)	11/12 92%	70/71 (99%)
CD3	2/2 (100%)	4/4 (100%)	3/3 (100%)	4/4 (100%)	3/3 (100%)	44/44 (100%)	2/2 (100%)	7/7 (100%)	14/14 (100%)	83/83 (100%)
TCR$\gamma\delta$	2/2 (100%)	4/4 (100%)	3/3 (100%)	4/4 (100%)	3/3 (100%)	44/44 (100%)	2/2 (100%)	7/7 (100%)	14/14 (100%)	83/83 (100%)
CD4	0/2 (0%)	0/4 (0%)	0/3 (0%)	0/4 (0%)	0/3 (0%)	0/44 (0%)	0/2 (0%)	0/7 (0%)	0/12 (0%)	0/83 (0%)
CD5	1/2 (50%)	NT	NT	NT	2/3 (67%)	37/44 (85%)	1/2 (50%)	2/7 (29%)*	9/13 (69%)	52/71 (73%)
CD7	2/2 (100%)	NT	NT	NT	3/3 (100%)	41/44 (93%)	1/1 (100%)	7/7 (100%)	11/13 (85%)	65/70 (93%)
CD8	0/2 (0%)	2/4 (50%)	1/3 (33%)	3/4 (75%)	2/3 (67%)	29/44 (66%)	1/2 (50%)	0/7 (0%)	6/14 (43%)	44/83 (53%)
CD11b	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NA (58%)	NT	NT	NT	NA (58%)
CD11c	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NA (83%)	NT	NT	NT	NA (83%)
CD16	1/2 (50%)	2/4 (50%)	1/3 (33%)	4/4 (100%)	2/3 (67%)	20/41 (49%)	0/2 (0%)	2/4 (50%)	3/8 (38%)	35/70 (50%)
CD56	0/2 (0%)	0/4 (0%)	0/3 (0%)	0/4 (0%)	1/3 (33%)	20/42 (48%)	0/2 (0%)	2/7 (29%)	2/11 (18%)	25/78 (32%)
CD57	2/2 (100%)	2/4 (50%)	NT	0/4 (0%)	3/3 (100%)	37/43 (86%)	2/2 (100%)	2/6 (33%)	12/13 (92%)	60/77 (78%)

Author, year	Sun, 1991	Scott, 1994	Kuipers, 1994	Makishima, 2003	Ahmad, 2005	Sandberg, 2006	Shaw, 2008	Chen, 2011	Yabe, 2015	Total
CD94	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	7/8 (88%)	7/8 (88%)
CD158	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	2/3 (67%) †	NT	2/3 (67%)
TiA1	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NA	7/7 (100%)	9/9 (100%)	16/16 (100%)
Granzyme B	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NT	NA	4/6 (67%)	9/9 (100%)	13/15 (87%)
HLA-DR	NT	4/4 (100%)	NT	NT	NT	NA (66%)	NA	NT	NA	NA (>66%)

Abbreviations: NA, results not available; NT, not tested.

Results are presented as number of cases in which the leukemic gamma/delta T cells expressed the mentioned molecule among the cases tested; the correspondent percentages of positive cases are indicated in parentheses.

The series from Bourgault-Rouxel et al., 2008 [27] was excluded because phenotypic data were not presented in detail. In this series, GDTLGLL cells had a CD3+/CD4-/CD8+/CD16+/CD57+ phenotype, in 50% of cases

* Two cases were partially dim positive for CD5

† The expression of the killer cell receptors (KIR) CD158a, CD158b and CD158e was assessed by flow cytometry in 3 cases. One case showed exclusive expression of a single KIR antigen (CD158b); another case demonstrated aberrant co-expression of 2 KIR antigens (CD158a and CD158e) with uniform intensities in the same cell population; the remaining case showed absent expression of all 3 KIR antigens.

Table S5. *STAT3* and *STAT5B* mutations in T-cell large granular lymphocyte leukemia

Subtype	CD8+ TCR- $\alpha\beta$ +	CD4+ TCR- $\alpha\beta$ +	CD4+ TCR- $\alpha\beta$ +	CD4+ TCR- $\alpha\beta$ +										
Author, year	Koskela, 2012 *	Jerez, 2012 †	Rajala, 2013 ‡	Ohgami, 2013 §	Rajala, 2015 ¶	Shi, 2017 **	Andersson, 2016 ††	Teramo A, 2017 ‡‡	Total	Andersson, 2016 ††	Teramo A, 2017 ‡‡	Total	Total	
References	[118]	[117]	[119]	[120]	[123]	[124]	[125]	[126]		[125]	[126]			-
<i>STAT3</i> MUTATIONS (SH2: Exons 20, 21)	31/77 (40.3%)	33/120 (27.5%)	NA	4/36 (11.1%)	75/174 (43.1%)	18/36 (50.0%)	37/95 (38.9%)	38/68 (55.8%)	236/606 (38.9%)	NA	0/33 (0%)	0/33 (0%)	236/639 (36.9%)	
<i>STAT3</i> Domains	SH2	SH2	NA	SH2			NA	SH2		NA	SH2	0		
<i>STAT3</i> Exons	19-24	19-24		19-24				21			21			
S614R (SH2)	0	3	NA	0	0	0	NA	0	3	NA	0	0	3	
G618R (SH2)	0	0	NA	0	0	0	NA	0	0	NA	0	0	0	
E638Q (SH2)	0	0	NA	0	0	1	NA	0	1	NA	0	0	1	
Y640F (SH2)	13	14	NA	2	32	12	NA	24	97	NA	0	0	97	
N647I (SH2)	3	1	NA	0	2	3	NA	1	10	NA	0	0	10	
G656_Y657insY (SH2)	0	0	NA	0	0	0	NA	1	1	NA	0	0	1	
K657R (SH2)	0	0	NA	0	0	1	NA	0	1	NA	0	0	1	
Y657 K658 ins NS (SH2)	0	0	NA	0	1	0	NA	0	1	NA	0	0	1	
Y657 ins NS (SH2)	0	0	NA	0	1	0	NA	0	1	NA	0	0	1	
K658M (SH2)	0	1	NA	0	0	0	NA	0	1	NA	0	0	1	
K658N (SH2)	0	0	NA	0	1	0	NA	0	1	NA	0	0	1	
K658R + I659_M660insL	0	0	NA	0	0	0	NA	1	1	NA	0	0	1	
I659L (SH2)	0	0	NA	0	0	1	NA	0	1	NA	0	0	1	
D661H (SH2)	1	0	NA	0	1	0	NA	0	2	NA	0	0	2	
D661I (SH2)	0	0	NA	0	0	0	NA	0	0	NA	0	0	0	
D661V (SH2)	7	3	NA	0	4	0	NA	1	15	NA	0	0	15	
D661Y (SH2)	7	12	NA	2	16	0	NA	9	46	NA	0	0	46	
A662_N663delinsH (SH2)	0	0	NA	0	0	0	NA	1	1	NA	0	0	1	

Subtype	CD8+ TCR-αβ+	CD8+ TCR-αβ+	CD8+ TCR-αβ+	CD8+ TCR-αβ+	CD8+ TCR-αβ+	CD8+ TCR-αβ+	CD8+ TCR-αβ+	CD8+ TCR-αβ+	CD8+ TCR-αβ+	CD8+ TCR-αβ+	CD4+ TCR-αβ+ ††	CD4+ TCR-αβ+ ‡‡	CD4+ TCR-αβ+	
Author, year	Koskela, 2012 *	Jerez, 2012 †	Rajala, 2013 ‡	Ohgami, 2013 §	Rajala, 2015 ¶	Shi, 2017 **	Andersson, 2016 ††	Teramo A, 2017 ‡‡	Total	Andersson, 2016 ††	Teramo A, 2017 ‡‡	Total	Total	
References	[118]	[117]	[119]	[120]	[123]	[124]	[125]	[126]		[125]	[126]			-
STAT5B MUTATIONS	NA	0/20 (0.0%)	3/171 (1.8%)	NA	NA	NA	0/95 (0.0%)	0/68 (0.0%)	5/354 (1.4%)	6/11 (54.5%)	5/33 (15.1%)	11/44 (25.0%)	16/398 (4.0%)	
STAT5B Domains	NA	SH2	SH2	NA	NA	NA	SH2, TA	SH2, TA		SH2, TA	SH2, TA			
STAT5B Exons			15-18				14-19	16-18		14-19	16-18			
E579K (SH2)	NA	0	0	NA	NA	NA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
N642H (SH2)	NA	0	1	NA	NA	NA	0	0	1	3	2	5	6	
Y665F (SH2)	NA	0	2	NA	NA	NA	0	0	2	1	2	3	5	
I704L (SH2)	NA	0	0	NA	NA	NA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Q706L (TA)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	0	0	1	1	2	2	
V712E (TA)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
S715F (TA)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	

Abbreviations: AB, alpha/beta; ABTLGLL, alpha/beta T cell large granular lymphocyte leukemia; ACT, activating mutation; CLPDNK, chronic lymphoproliferative disorders of NK cells; SH2, Src Homology 2 domain; STAT, signal transducer and activator of transcription; TA, transcriptional activation domain; TLGLL, T-cell large granular lymphocyte leukemia.

Cases of CLPDNK analyzed in these series were excluded from data presented in the table.

Data are presented as absolute and relative (%) frequencies of TLGLL cases showing *STAT3* and *STAT5B* mutations among the total number of TLGLL cases analyzed in each disease category, and as absolute and relative (%) frequencies of the specific *STAT3* and *STAT5B* mutations among the total number of *STAT3* and *STAT5B* mutations found, respectively.

FATHMM prediction is indicated inside brackets [] (Pathogenic, score)

* **Koskela et al., 2012 [118]:** All cases analyzed in this series were CD8+ ABTLGLL. Next-generation exome sequencing to identify somatic *STAT3* mutations, followed by validation with Sanger sequencing. Among the 31 cases with *STAT3* mutations, recurrent mutational hot spots included Y640F in 13 (17%), D661V in 7 (9%), D661Y in 7 (9%), and N647I in 3 (4%). All mutations were in exon 21, encoding the SH2 domain, which mediates the dimerization and activation of STAT protein. Patients with *STAT3* mutations presented more often with neutropenia and rheumatoid arthritis than did patients without these mutations (77% vs 50% and 26% vs. 6%).

† **Jerez et al., 2012 [117]:** This series included 50 CLPDNK and 120 TLGLL; from the 120 TLGLL cases analyzed, only 118 were CD8+ ABTLGLL and 2 were GDTLGLL. Mutations were detected using PCR direct sequencing assays. The presence of D661Y and Y640F mutations non-detectable by direct sequencing was determined by a DNA tetra-primer amplification refractory mutation system (ARMS) assay. *STAT3* mutations were observed in 15 out of 50 patients with CLPDNK (30%) and 33 out of 120 patients with TLGLL (27%). One of two GDTLGLL cases included in this study was mutated. All mutations were in the domain of *STAT3* (residues 585-688) that shares homology with SH2 domains, dimerization via binding of a phosphotyrosine residue. Two mutations, Y640F and D661Y, accounted for 80% of the somatic variations found. Patients with *STAT3* mutations are characterized by symptomatic disease and multiple treatments. No additional somatic mutations were identified in the SH2 domain of other STAT family members (*STAT1*, *STAT2*, *STAT4*, *STAT5A*, *STAT5B*, and *STAT6*) and in a sub-cohort of 20 *STAT3*-mutations negative cases TLGLL. * Two patients had GDTLGLL; one of these patients had the Y640F *STAT3* mutation; one patient harbored 2 *STAT3* mutations (D661Y and Y640F); *STAT5B* mutations were studied in 20 *STAT3* negative TLGLL cases.

‡ **Rajala et al., 2013 [119]:** Using exome and transcriptome sequencing, a recurrent, somatic missense mutation (Y665F) in the SH2 domain of the *STAT5B* gene was first identified in 2 *STAT3* mutation negative CD8+ ABTLGLL patients. Targeted amplicon sequencing of 171 TLGLL revealed 1 additional case having *STAT5B* N642H mutation, corresponding to a patient with CD8+ ABTLGLL with an aggressive clinical course. ** The patient with the *STAT5B* N642H mutation, was reported to have an aggressive CD3+ TCRαβ+ CD8+ CD56+ ABTLGLL manifesting as massive splenomegaly, pancytopenia and neutropenia; this patient had hyperleukocytosis (WBC 90 x 10⁹/L) with hyperlymphocytosis (Lymphocytes 85.5 x 10⁹/L) at the diagnosis and the time of the study; he died despite receiving systemic chemotherapy, and the autopsy indicated extensive lymphocyte infiltration in the bone marrow, stomach, small bowel, lungs, liver, spleen, and lymph nodes. In the same study, the only patient with NK-cell LGLL having a *STAT5B* N642H mutation also had an aggressive clinical course. This patient also had hyperleukocytosis (WBC 164.7 x 10⁹/L) with hyperlymphocytosis (131.8 x 10⁹/L) at the diagnosis and at the time of the study, and was reported to have NK-LGLL leukemia with normal karyotype, neutropenia, hemolytic anemia, and splenomegaly; he was treated by splenectomy, which induced hematologic remission, but after 7 years of follow-up he developed LGL leukemia refractory to chemotherapy. Both patients with the *STAT5B* mutation Y665F had CD8+ CD56+ ABTLGLL with mild lymphocytosis and an indolent clinical course, without need for treatment (18 months of follow-up).

§ **Ohgami et al., 2013 [120]:** PCR amplification of *STAT3* was performed in samples from 36 patients with TLGLL, using primers covering exons 19–24, corresponding to the SH2 domain. Among the 4 positive cases, two harbored the Y640F mutation and two contained the D661Y mutation.

¶ **Rajala et al, 2015** [123]: From the 75 CD8+ ABTLGLL patients having *STAT3* mutations (out of 174 CD8+ ABLGLL patients analyzed), 3 patients had multiple *STAT3* mutations in the same clone, 14 patients had multiple *STAT* mutations in different LGL clones, and 58 patients had one *STAT3* mutation.

** **Shi et al, 2017** [124]: Three patients had GDTLGLL, and two of them had *STAT3* mutations (non-specified in the manuscript).

†† **Andersson et al, 2016** [125]: Exome sequencing was performed on 3 CD4+ ABTLGLL patients' sorted tumor (CD4+CD8-/+) and somatic missense mutations *STAT5B* gene were identified in 2 cases: one patient had a Q706L mutation and another patient displayed a S715F mutation; the third patient with CD4+ ABTLGLL did not show any mutations in *STAT5B* or *STAT3* genes. To elucidate whether *STAT5B* mutations are more prevalent in CD4+ ABTLGLL cases, deep amplicon sequencing was used for screening of the SH2 and TA domains of *STAT5B* in 8 CD4+ ABTLGLL and 95 CD8+ ABTLGLL (*STAT3* mutated: n=37; *STAT3* non-mutated: n= 58). Targeted *STAT5B* amplicon sequencing covering exons 14 to 19 was done with an in-house– developed deep amplicon sequencing panel. Additionally, the same regions were screened with Sanger sequencing in Japanese and Chinese LGLL consisting of CD8+ ABTLGLL and CLPDNK cases (n=57). None of the patients with CD8+ ABTLGLL or CLPDNK had *STAT5B* mutations. In contrast, 4 of 8 CD4+ ABTLGLL. Of the 4 patients with *STAT5B* mutations, 3 possessed the N642H mutation and 1 the Y665F mutation.

***** Detailed data about the *STAT3* mutations in patients with CD8+ ABTLGLL are not provided in the manuscript. Data about the *STAT3* mutations in patients with CD4+ ABTLGLL are not provided in the manuscript.

‡‡ **Teramo et al, 2017** [126]: The cohort included 101 ABTLGLL patients (68 CD8+/CD4- and 33 CD4+/CD8±)

Table S6. *STAT3* and *STAT5B* mutations in gamma/delta T cell lymphoma

Lymphoma subtype	HSGDTCL		PCGDTCL	IGDTCL (only MEITCL)			
Author, year	Nicolae, 2014 *	Küçük, 2015 †	Küçük, 2015 †	Küçük, 2015 †	Nairismägi, 2016 ‡	Nicolae, 2016 §	Total
References	[168]	[169]	[169]	[169]	[198]	[199]	-
<i>STAT3</i> MUTATIONS	2/21	0/9	2/15	0/16 (0/16)	NA (NA)	3/14 (3/8)	7/75 (7/69)
(SH2: 554-715)	9.5%	0.0%	13.3%	0.0% (0.0%)	NA (NA)	21.4% (37.5%)	9.3% (10.1%)
<i>STAT3</i> domains	SH2	SH2	SH2	SH2	NA	SH2	SH2
<i>STAT3</i> aa residues	614-661	554-715	554-715	554-715	NA	585-688	
S614R (SH2)	0	0	0	0	NA	1 (1)	1 (1)
E616G (SH2)	0	0	0	0	NA	1 (1)	1 (1)
G618R (SH2)	0	0	1	0	NA	0	1 (1)
Y640F (SH2)	1	0	1	0	NA	0	2 (1)
N647I (SH2)	0	0	0	0	NA	0	0
E638Q (SH2)	0	0	0	0	NA	0	0
K657R (SH2)	0	0	0	0	NA	0	0
Y657 K658 ins NS (SH2)	0	0	0	0	NA	0	0
Y657 ins NS (SH2)	0	0	0	0	NA	0	0
K658M (SH2)	0	0	0	0	NA	0	0
K658N (SH2)	0	0	0	0	NA	0	0
I659L (SH2)	0	0	0	0	NA	0	0
D661H (SH2)	0	0	0	0	NA	0	0
D661I (SH2)	0	0	0	0	NA	0	0
D661V (SH2)	0	0	0	0	NA	0	0
D661Y (SH2)	1	0	0	0	NA	1 (1)	2 (2)
<i>STAT5B</i> MUTATIONS	7/21	4/9	4/15	7/16 (7/16)	10/16 (10/16)	4/14 (3/8)	36/91 (35/85)
(SH2: 592-685 aa)	33.3%	44.4%	26.7%	43.8% (43.8%)	62.5% (62.5%)	42.8% (37.5%)	39.6 (41.2%)
(TA: 707-787 aa)							
<i>STAT5B</i> Domains	SH2	SH2	SH2	SH2	SH2, TA	SH2	
<i>STAT5B</i> Aa Residues	642-665	573-717	573-717	573-717	636-657; 710-733	573-717	
E579K (SH2)	NA	0	1	0	NA	0	1 (1)
N642H (SH2)	7	3	3	7 (7)	9 (9)	4 (3)	33 (32)
Y665F (SH2)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
I704L (SH2)	NA	1	0	0	0	0	1 (1)
Q706L (TA)	NA	0	0	0	NA	0	0
V712E (TA)	0	0	0	0	1 (1)	0	1 (1)
S715F (TA)	NA	0	0	0	0	0	0

Abbreviations: EATCL, Enteropathy-associated T-cell lymphoma; IGDTCCL, intestinal gamma/delta T cell lymphoma; ENKTL, extranodal NK/T cell lymphoma; GD, gamma/delta; GDTCL, gamma/delta T cell lymphoma; HSGDTCL, hepatosplenic gamma/delta T cell lymphoma; MEITCL, monomorphic epitheliotropic intestinal T-cell lymphoma; PCGDTCL, primary cutaneous gamma/delta T cell lymphoma; SH2, Src Homology 2 domain; STAT, signal transducer and activator of transcription; TA, transcriptional activation domain.

Cases of ENKTL nasal type analyzed in this series were excluded from data presented in the table.

* **Nicolae et al, 2014 [168]**: Targeted analysis for *STAT3* mutations located between codons 614 and 661, and for *STAT5B* mutations located between codons 642 and 665 was performed on involved spleens using pyrosequencing. All cases with *STAT5B* mutations shared the same hot spot mutation (N642H). Two additional cases had a *STAT3* somatic missense mutation (D661Y and Y640F). *STAT5B* mutated cases had a higher expression of CD56, compared to wild-type cases (85% vs 28%).

† **Küçük et al, 2015 [169]**: Whole-transcriptome sequencing, exome sequencing or targeted Sanger sequencing was applied on 40 GDTCL: 15 PCGDTCL, 9 HSGDTCL, and 16 IGDTCCL (EATCL type II / MEITCL). *STAT5B* activating mutations in the SH2 domain were present in 4 PCGDTCL (26.7%) (N642H, 3 cases; E579K, 1 case), 4 HSTCL (44.9%) (N642H, 3 cases; I704L, 1 case) and 7 IGDTCCL (43.8%) (N642H, 7 cases). In contrast, *STAT3* mutations were present in only 2 of the 15 (13.3%) PCGDTCL (Y640F and G618R, one case each), and in none of the HSGDTCL and IGDTCCL

‡ **Nairismägi et al, 2016 [198]**: Whole-exome sequencing was applied on 4 EATCL type II / MEITCL cases / normal pairs, followed by amplicon deep sequencing of 42 tumor samples, totalizing 46 EATCL type II / MEITCL cases studied (11 TCR- $\alpha\beta$ +, 16 TCR- $\gamma\delta$ +, 4 TCR double negative, 12 TCR double-positive cases and 3 cases not tested for TCR. *STAT5B* mutations were present in 63% of all cases studied (29/46), and in 62.5% of the TCR- $\gamma\delta$ + cases (10/16)

§ **Nicolae et al, 2016 [199]**: A target NFS strategy was used to analyze 34 cases of ITCL (10 EATCL, 20 MEITCL and 4 PTCLs), from which 14 cases were of $\gamma\delta$ Tc (4 EATCL, 8 MEITCL and 2 PTCL, NOS), for the presence of mutations in 38 genes, including *STAT3* and *STAT5B*. *STAT5B* mutations were found in 35.0% (7/20) MEITCL (37.5% if considering only GDTCL cases), but in only 10% of EATCL (1/10 cases, none of which were GDTCL).

